

General Assembly Activity Report & News

Public version

Uwe Kies
Secretary General, InnovaWood

Tulln, Austria, 6 May 2026

State of the network: Annual report 2025/2026

1. Minutes of GA 2025
2. Welcome to new members
3. A short history of InnovaWood
4. Financial Report & Budget
5. Strategy Process
6. EU Projects
7. IW Internal Projects
8. Summary & Conclusions

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Minutes GA 2025

 InnovaWood
connect share influence

23rd InnovaWood General Assembly
13 - 15 May 2025 in Kastoria, Greece

Minutes

InnovaWood GA members group photo, 13 May 2025

Hosted by

 CluBE
Cluster of Bioeconomy & Environment
of Western Macedonia

INNOVAWOOD • European Forestry House • 66 Rue du Luxembourg • 1000 Brussels • Belgium
asbl no. 828085535 • office@innovawood.com

InnovaWood GA, hosted by CluBE in Kastoria, Greece, 13-15 May 2025

Minutes (PDF) sent per mail 10/04/2025: [Download](#)

Web article: <https://innovawood.com/general-assemblies/2025ga>

Past GAs: <https://innovawood.com/general-assemblies>

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Membership : New members 2025/26

Manifaktura srl,
Italy

GVA National Reference Centre
for Wood and Cork Processing
and Installation, Spain

HFA Holzforchung Austria
Austrian Forest Products
Research Society

Welcome
to our
network !

CMD
Galician Wood and
Design Cluster,
Spain

WoodWorks! Cluster,
Norway

FING-UDELAR
Faculty of Engineering,
University of the Republic,
Uruguay

Membership : New members 2025/26

Manifaktura srl, Italy

manifaktura.net

Francesco Balducci, PhD Eng

Co-founder Manifaktura srl

Alessandra Cecchini, MSc

Co-founder Manifaktura srl

Membership : New members 2025/26

GVA - National Reference Centre for Wood and Cork Processing and Installation, LABORA Vocational Training Centre, Spain

labora.gva.es/en/web/crn-paterna/nuestro-centro

Celia Ruiz Flores

Director, National Reference Centre for Wood and Cork Processing and Installation

Membership : New members 2025/26

Holzforschung Austria Austrian Forest Products Research Society

holzforschung.at

Gerhard Grill

Sylvia Polleres

Mira Kirchner

Membership : New members 2025/26

CMD - Galician Wood and Design Cluster, Spain

clustermadeira.com

Susana Vázquez
Head of Administration

Luis Suárez
Project Manager

Laura Rodríguez
Head of Communication

Ricardo González
Cluster Manager

Membership : New members 2025/26

WoodWorks! Cluster, Norway

woodworkscluster.no

Vibeke Tronstad
CEO

Kjersti Kinderås
Project manager

Knut Magnar Sandland
Project manager building

Lars Johansson
Project manager fiber

Membership : New members 2025/26

FING-UDELAR - Faculty of Engineering, University of the Republic
Multidisciplinary Timber Research Group, Uruguay

fing.edu.uy

Dr. Daniel Godoy
dgodoy@fing.edu.uy

PhD Laura Moya
moya@ort.edu.uy

ChE. Silvia Böthig
sbothig@latitud.org.uy

MSc. Gastón Bruzzzone
gbruzzzone@fagro.edu.uy

Membership : New members 2025/26

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A short history of IW 2001

Launch of the IW initiative, joining 4 networks, about 100 members
First EU project under FP5: IW Research Database

A short history of IW 2002

The InnovaWood Initiative

A new confederation of the four European networks: a mechanism to add value and create a synergy between projects serving the Forestry, Wood and Furniture sector

Eurowood European Wood Research Association, Brussels

EuroLigna Training institutions of Wood Technology and Furniture

Eurifi Furniture, Research and Development institutions

Eurofortech Education, Training and Technology Transfer in the Forestry and Wood sector

We still follow the same core idea.

InnovaWood launch: presentation from 2002

Lessons from our Experiences

- Network development is a long hard task
- Extremely difficult to survive on project funding alone – need institutional support / sponsorship
- Project development and mangement requires professional approach
- Language issues are very important
- Effective dissemination is one of the most difficult aspects of projects
- Sectoral approach is highly effective
- Critical mass and a full-time secretariat are essential for long-term maintenance and development of products
- **Against this background we have created InnovaWood**

We are still doing it.

Today this is our USP !

We have grown considerably.

A short history of IW 2009

General Assembly in Valencia, Spain, hosted by AIDIMA

A short history of IW 2010

MOD 2.2

 Copie à publier aux annexes du Moniteur belge après dépôt de l'acte

Réservé au Moniteur belge

DÉPOSÉ AU GREFFE DU TRIBUNAL DE COMMERCE DE BRUXELLES, LE 27-07-2010
LE GREFFIER,

N° d'entreprise : 828 085 535

Dénomination (en entier) : **InnovaWood**

(en abrégé) :

Forme juridique : Association Sans But Lucratif

Siège : rue du Luxembourg, 66, à 1000 Bruxelles

Objet de l'acte : **Constitution - statuts - nominations**

Il résulte d'un acte reçu par Maître Isabelle RAES, notaire associée, membre de la société civile sous forme de société privée à responsabilité limitée "DEPUYT & RAES", ayant son siège à MotenbEEK-Saint-Jean, le 23 juillet 2010 et déposé au greffe du Tribunal de Commerce de Bruxelles avant l'accomplissement des formalités d'enregistrement, que :

- Une association sans but lucratif a été fondée sous la dénomination "InnovaWood", par les personnes morale et physiques suivantes :
 - L'association de droit espagnol « ASOCIACION DE INVESTIGACION Y DESARROLLO EN LA INDUSTRIA DEL MUEBLE Y AFINES », en abrégé « AIDIMA », ayant son siège social à 46980 Valencia (Espagne), Paterna, Parc Tecnològic, calle Benjamin Franklin 13 ;
 - Madame RATAJCZAK Ewa, née à Leszno (Pologne) le 17 janvier 1955, de nationalité polonaise, domiciliée à Paslecka 9, 60-454 Poznan, Pologne ;
 - Monsieur IRLE Mark Anthony, né à Woolwich (Royaume-Uni) le 21 décembre 1960, de nationalité britannique, domicilié à rue des vignes 21, 44470 Thouare, France ;
 - Monsieur VAN ACKER Joris Camiel René, né à Beernem le 15 août 1960, domicilié à 9000 Gent, Dampoortstraat 92, Belgique ;
 - Monsieur WELLING Johannes, né à Duisburg (Allemagne) le 16 février 1954, de nationalité allemande, domicilié à Wohltorferstrasse 46A, Reinbek, Allemagne ;
 - Madame PAAVILAINEN Leena Marjatta, née à Lahti (Finlande) le 8 juin 1954, de nationalité finlandaise, domiciliée à Kiuruntie 13 B, 04320 Tuusula, Finlande, et
 - Monsieur MC GOWAN Denis Patrick, né à Ballyshannon (Irlande) le 6 octobre 1956, de nationalité irlandaise, domicilié à Deepark Road 33, Castleknock, Dublin 15, Irlande.

Registered as Non-Profit « Association Sans But Lucratif » (ASBL) in Brussels, Belgium

A short history of IW 2014

General Assembly in Tulln, Austria, hosted by BOKU & Wood K plus

A short history of IW 2017

SSP meeting, Koper, Slovenia, 2017

Executive Board meeting, Ljubljana, 2018

New President, new Secretary General, new Executive Board

A short history of IW 2019 - 2025

Hamburg, Germany, 2019

Kastoria, Greece, 2025

Porto, Portugal, 2022

The General Assemblies has become
our main members' event.

A short history of IW 2019 - 2025

Budapest, 2019

Porto, 2022

The Secretariat has grown from
2 to 11 persons (from 1.5 to 8 FTE) !

Lacanau, 2025

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InnovaWood Secretariat

Uwe Kies
Secretary
General

Oliver Jancke
Business
Manager

Florence Kuijl
Communications
Manager

Vanesa Baño
Senior
Researcher

Radmila Ustych
Senior Project
Manager

Mercedes Rois
Office Manager

Patrycja Zatoń
Project Manager

Eva Čeh
Creative Manager

Claudio Biondi
Project Manager

Peter Romih
Junior Researcher

Anna Cosp Garcia
Junior Researcher

Administration

Membership

Communication

Research

IW membership 2026

- Total: **85** members in **30** countries
- **6** new members: 1 RTO, 1 university, 2 clusters, 2 others
- 2 left: 1 university, 1 other
- since 2017 (past 9 years): **+ 36** new members (+73%)

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Our Portfolio

CONNECT

Members Networking and Guidance

- General Assembly
- Events calendar
- Funding navigator
- Partnering & proposals
- Project support & studies

SHARE

R&I Communication and Dissemination

- Events hosting
- Stakeholder engagement
- Social media
- Publications
- Repositories

INFLUENCE

Policy Communication and Advocacy

- Policy platforms & alliances
- Policy briefs & position papers
- Policy workshops & events
- Policy navigator
- Innovation databases

Our Vision

What we strive to achieve

InnovaWood is Europe's wood research, innovation, and education **community** — where **isolated efforts** become **collective strength**, where **opportunities** are found, and **scientific impact** is made.

 COMMUNITY

 OPPORTUNITIES FOUND

 COLLECTIVE STRENGTH

 SCIENTIFIC IMPACT

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EU projects

Funded by the European Union

1st European Conference on Small Forest Holdings, FAO HQ, Rome, 20-22 May 2025

Sustainable Management models and value chains for small forests

Coordinator

Fundacion Centro De Servicios Y Promocion Forestal Y De Su Industria De Castilla Y Leon (CESEFOR)

Type	Budget	Partners	Duration
RIA	€ 5.4 M	15	2024-2027 (4 years)

Weblinks

- smurfproject.eu
- cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101135516
- linkedin.com/company/smurfproject

Alvaro Picardo

WOOD STOCK

SIX LIVING LABS

InnoRenew IR

The Green Village TUD

Living Lab GALWAY GALWAY

Resilient Habitat UBx

Trondheim Living Lab NTNU

Living Lab TUL TUL

Climate-smart use of underutilised wood in construction

Coordinator
University of Gent, Woodlab

Type	Budget	Partners	Duration
RIA	€ 6.9 M	12	2024-2028 (4 years)

Weblinks
woodstockproject.eu
cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101181021
linkedin.com/company/woodstockproject

Liselotte de Ligne

FRANCESCA

Circular Efficiency Strategies for Furniture Renewal

Coordinator
Technological Center for Furniture and Wood of the Region of Murcia (CETEM)

Type	Budget	Partners	Duration
IA	€ 5.4 M	15	2025-2028 (4 years)

Weblinks

- francesca.eco
- cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101182003
- linkedin.com/company/horizonfrancesca

Juan José Ortega Gras

EcoReFibre

Ecological Solutions for Recovery of Secondary Raw Materials from Post-consumer Fibreboards

Coordinator
Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU)

<i>Type</i>	<i>Budget</i>	<i>Partners</i>	<i>Duration</i>
IA	€ 15.8 M	21	2022-2026 (4.5 years)

Weblinks
ecorefibre.eu
cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101057473
linkedin.com/company/ecorefibre

Stergios Adamopoulos

EcoReFibre

EcoReFibre

UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY AND MARKET POTENTIAL FROM WOOD WASTE

STRATEGIC ROADMAP

EcoReFibre Strategic Roadmap

- Final main publication with key technical and policy recommendation
- Co-authored with European Panel Federation (EPF)
- DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17473126>

EcoReFibre

Funded by the European Union

POLICY CONFERENCE

UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY AND MARKET POTENTIAL FROM WOOD WASTE

March 25, 2026, 10:00-16:00 CET
THE SQUARE - Convention Centre Brussels, Belgium

EUROPEAN PANEL FEDERATION
WOOD-BASED PANELS

Innovawood

Policy Conference in Brussels

- 70 participants
- European Commission DG GROW & DG CLIMA Head of Units as speakers
- Presentation of the Strategic Roadmap, stakeholder workshop to collect feedback and input
- Press release & news article ecorefibre.eu/2026/03/31/pr-policyconference26

EcoReFibre animation video clip

- <https://youtu.be/QrtMRvSRung>
- Transforming complex research ideas into engaging storytelling: 4-years project results into 2.5 minutes
- Animation clip in visual style, co-designed by researchers and coms team
- Read more about it: <https://innovawood.com/erf-animation>

Eva Čeh
Creative Director

New European Bauhaus Academy

New European Bauhaus Academy

© dRMM / de Rijke

Maderaula © CESEFOR

© European Commission

New European Bauhaus Academy Alliance : open skills platform for the construction ecosystem

Coordinator
University of Primorska – InnoRenew CoE / NEBAP Hub

<i>Type</i>	<i>Budget</i>	<i>Partners</i>	<i>Duration</i>
CSA	€ 1.0 M	21	2024-2026 (2 years)

Weblinks

- neb.academy
- cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101160532
- linkedin.com/company/neb-academy

Andreja Kutnar

New European Bauhaus Academy

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference

Knowledge, Skills, and Innovation in sustainable construction for a resilient future of Europe

Co-hosted by:

Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC)
InnovaWood
University of Primorska

Barcelona,
February 27, 2026

City Council of Barcelona's
Culture and Education Centre

Conference co-organised together with InnovaWood members

- 80 participants, 2 keynotes, 1 panel discussion, 10 PechaKucha presentations, 1 networking session
- Showcasing good practices in skills and training for sustainable construction
- Forum for exchange with NEBA Alliance, other NEB projects, the NEB team at JRC, and stakeholders

Article: [innovawood.com/nebacademyconference26](https://www.innovawood.com/nebacademyconference26)

All presentations: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18853140>

Recordings : [Youtube video playlist](#)

New European Bauhaus Academy

Conference co-organised together with InnovaWood members

- 80 participants, 2 keynotes, 1 panel discussion, 10 PechaKucha presentations, 1 networking session
- Showcasing good practices in skills and training for sustainable construction
- Forum for exchange for NEBA Alliance, other NEB projects, stakeholders, and the NEB Unit of the JRC

Article: [innovawood.com/nebacademyconference26](https://www.innovawood.com/nebacademyconference26)
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What are internal projects ?

- **Specific actions of strategic interest for InnovaWood**

- Build up our special competences and USP as European network
- Create synergies from funded projects for developing IW
- Continuously grow our databases to feed member services and advocacy

- Ongoing - Initiated - Ideas

1. IW Members Register
2. Circular Economy meetings series
3. ETA Innovations database
4. EU Policy Navigator
5. WoodPoP Taskforce Wood Innovation
6. EU projects database / CORDIS query

IW Members Register

- IW contact database: members, partners, stakeholders
- IW member infosheets: projects, publications, infrastructures
- Goal: Make it accessible for all members

Start | Contacts | Projects

Search: _____ Year: 2025 | 2025 | Kw: IW mailing list 1 - ALL MEMBERS | Sector: | Geo: | Source: | Class: | Update: | Reset: |

71 | Type: | hide staff: on | hide old: | L1 L2 P1 | BP 1 2 3

AIDIMME - Furniture, Wood, Packaging and Metal-Mecanic Technology Institute, José Luis Millá Tamarit, R&D Techni	RTO Research & Technical O	Wood science, technology, ii	IW full SSP memb
BaskEgur - Baskegur Association, Zamudio Bizkaia, Spain	Cluster organizations	Wood science, technology, ii	IW full members
BFH-AHB - Berne University of Applied Science, Department of Architecture, Woc	Technical Universities & High	Wood science, technology, ii	IW full SSP memb
BOKU - University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Institute of Wood Tech	University research institute	Wood science, technology, ii	IW full members
CATAS - CATAS SpA, San Giovanni al Natisone, Italy	RTO Research & Technical O	Furniture, interior	IW full members
CESEFOR - Castilla y León Forest and Wood industries Services Center Foundatio	RTO Research & Technical O	Wood science, technology, ii	IW full members
CETEM - Centre for Technology of Furniture and Wood Industry in Murcia region	RTO Research & Technical O	Furniture, interior	IW full members
CETEMAS - Forest and Wood Technology Research Centre, 33936, Spain	RTO Research & Technical O	Forestry, forest management	IW full members
CFPIMM - Vocational Training Centre for the Wood and Furniture Industries, Lori	VET, Professional Schools	Furniture, interior	IW full members
CluBE - Bioeconomy and Environment Cluster of Western Macedonia, Kozani, Gr	Cluster organizations	> Bioenergy, biofuels, bio-o	IW full SSP memb

Abbr: AIDIMME | Member no.: 065 | ID: 25 | Staff members: José Luis Millá Tamarit, Amparo Roca, Asun Perez, Carlos Soriano, Charo Lázaro, Firas Loutfi M, Guillermo Ma, Irene Beleña, Javier Agraz B, Jose Chaparr

Name: Asociación de Investigación y desarrollo en la Industria c | Title: R&D Technician | ID: 4294 | AIDIMME

Engl. Furniture, Wood, Packaging and Metal-Mecanic Technol | Surname: Millá Tamarit

Adr.1: P.O. Box 50 | Email: jlmilla@aidimme.es | jlr

Adr.2: Parque Tecnológico | Tel/Cell: |

Adr.3: C/ Benjamín Franklin, 13 | Web: |

City: 46980 | Paterna (Valenc) | Spain |

Type: RTO Research & Technical | VAT: ESG46261590 |

Projects: Best practices

Xyloreach - E	q115a	2001-200
CHANGE-UP -	q191a	2005-200
DIPP - Develo	q115b	2005-200
Innovawood	q115b	2005-200
Innovawood	q182	2006-200
Modelpack -	q115b	2006-200
WoodSens - f	q121b	2010-201
Celluwood - l	q115c	2011-201
FUNES - FUR	q181	2014-201
ECAMOB - En	q191r	2014-201
EUROJOINER	q181	2015-201
WOODUAL -	q181	2015-201
MIMWOOD -	q181	2016-201
WRING - Woc	q191r	2016-202
LIFE-2-ACID	q191l	2017-202
WOODUAL -	q181	2018-202

Record: 1 of 1 | No Filter | Search

Reference projects
Instructions: Please list your top past and ongoing projects useful as reference. List at least 5.
These will be used to complement our R&I project database to be shared with members. Selected lists may also be shared with externals for networking & project development.

No	New? Updated?	Acronym	Start Year	End Year	Funding Programme	Number, Grant ID	Title	Keywords, main topics
1	Updated	Xyloreach	2001	2004	FP5	QLK5-CT-2001-00608	End-user access to European RTD for the forest and wood industries sector	R&I, competitiveness (in FBS)
2	Updated	CHANGE-UP	2005	2007	ESF	297	Change Management in the Upholstered Furniture Industry (US-2005-0297)	Furniture, interior
3	Updated	DIPP	2005	2008	FP5	12609	Development of Innovative Particleboard Panels for a better mechanical performance and a lower environmental impact	Wood-based panels, wood construction, recycling
4	Updated	Innovawood ISA	2005	2008	FP6	515044	An innovation strategy to integrate industry needs and research capability in the European forestry-wood chain	R&I, competitiveness (in FBS)
5	Updated	Innovawood Edu	2006	2008	LdV	6153170	Expanding good practice in vocational education and training in the Forestry-Wood Chain sector through the Innovawood network (LEO-LDVI-4-213370)	Education, skills, qualification (in FBS), VET vocational education and training
6	Updated	Modelpack	2006	2009	FP6	36299	Advanced quality prediction tool for knowledge-driven packaging design and manufacturing in European SMEs	Wood packaging
7	Updated	WoodSens	2010	2014	ERA-2-WWN2	era-WoodSe	Developing and implementing formaldehyde online-sensor systems in wood-based panel processing	Wood-based panels
8	Updated	Celluwood	2011	2014	CIP-ECO	277331	Laminated Strong Eco-Material for Building Construction made of Cellulose-Strengthened Wood (ECO/10/277331)	Wood construction
9	Updated	FUNES	2014	2017	Erasmus+	2014-1-ES01-KA202-004883	Furniture New European Skills 2020	Furniture, interior, Erasmus+
10	Updated	ECAMOB	2014	2018	ER-RMC		Enhancing the cascade of wood and by integrating an intensified mobilisation of forest resources - ER Raw Materials, Strategic Implementation Plan	Recycling, waste, sidestreams, end-of-life (wood)
11	Updated	EUROJOINER	2015	2017	Erasmus+	2015-1-ES01-KA202-015902	Mobility of Wood Workers (Joiners/Carpenters) across Europe	Furniture, interior, Erasmus+
12	Updated	WOODUAL	2015	2018	Erasmus+	2015-1-IT01-KA202-004701	Wood sector and Dual Learning for Youth Employment and Skills	Furniture, interior, Erasmus+

Patrycja Zatoń

Oliver Jancke

IW Circular Economy meeting series

Oliver Jancke

Eight meetings brought together a broad cross section of organisations and countries across the InnovaWood network.

Wood Innovation and Policy Research Group

Databases

Categorisation & analysis

Case studies

Reports & papers

Summaries & factsheets

Wood research & innovation landscape

Research centres, innovation networks, supporting initiatives, etc. in the European forest-based sector

EU policy navigator

European policy landscape and its relevance for the wood sector

EU wood industries

Mapping of EWP manufacturers of both mature and innovative products

ETA-certified innovative products

Identification and analysis of innovative wood construction products on the market

EU technical standards

Mapping of wood-related CEN EN standards and EOTA-EADs

Vanesa Baño

Peter Romih

Anna Cosp Garcia

Uwe Kies

Twin Transition for The Timber Industry

European Wood Policy Platform

Forest Fund
Republic of Austria

An initiative by the Federal Ministry
of Agriculture and Forestry, Climate
and Environmental Protection,
Regions and Water Management
Republic of Austria

With the support of:

European Wood Policy Platform : Towards a wood-based circular bioeconomy

- Pan-European policy dialogue initiative involving 27 countries, 45 stakeholders and industry organisations in one platform
- Voluntary knowledge exchange and joint advocacy actions

Weblinks

woodpop.eu

at.linkedin.com/company/european-wood-policy-platform-woodpop

Višnja Koščak
Secretariat Coordinator

European Wood Policy Platform

Forest Fund
Republic of Austria

An initiative by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Climate and Environmental Protection, Regions and Water Management Republic of Austria

With the support of:

European Wood Policy Platform: Policy Briefs addressing the European Commission

- [FP10 as the engine of decarbonisation and competitiveness](#)
 - Key recommendations for FP10: Wood is one of Europe's most strategic renewable resources, vital for regenerative growth and decarbonization.
- [The Wood-based sector requires a skilled workforce to propel Europe towards a sustainable future](#)
- [Contribution of WoodPoP to Advanced Materials Act](#)

Policy Brief
November 2025

Wood for Europe's future: FP10 as the engine of decarbonisation and competitiveness

To harness the full strategic potential of Europe's forests and wood resources for the green, digital, and circular transitions, FP10 should embed wood science, technology, and innovation across all relevant pillars. Coordinated investment in research excellence, industrial innovation, and skills development, prioritising the needs of SMEs, will strengthen resilience, accelerate decarbonisation, strengthen existing markets and unlock new markets. By integrating wood research infrastructures into European networks, fostering cross-sector collaboration, and aligning with New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles as well as EU Missions, Europe can position its forest-based industries as global leaders in sustainability and competitiveness. This is not only an environmental imperative but a socio-economic opportunity that demands decisive policy support and funding. Europe must act now.

WoodPoP call for actions
WoodPoP calls for urgent, coordinated action under FP10 to unlock the full potential of Europe's forestry and wood sector, a cornerstone for resilience, growth, climate neutrality and decarbonisation, circularity, and resilience. Despite being a vast, nationally available, reliable, renewable bioresource, it remains underused in terms of value added. Six priority challenges demand attention: Economic growth, climate adaptation, decarbonisation, digital traceability, inclusive governance, and skills development.

FP10 must drive research and innovation across its four pillars to scale low-carbon construction, develop circular wood systems, advance climate-smart and sustainable forestry, and deploy digital solutions for transparency. Europe cannot afford to miss this opportunity. FP10 must lead the way to enable a secure and scaling wood-based value chains as engines of competitiveness, social resilience and climate action.

Rationale
Wood is one of Europe's most strategic renewable resources, vital for regenerative growth and decarbonisation through carbon storage in solid wood, wood-based products, and biocomposites. The European wood sector contributes with € 1.114 billion significantly to EU's GDP and employs about 17.5 million people (Econmove, 2023, Basis economic data to the value chains of Forestry and Wood Industry in Europe). Fully aligned with the 'One Health' approach, the wood sector supports environmental, social, and economic sustainability, yet it remains underexploited in EU industry and climate strategies. This policy brief translates the WoodPoP Policy Paper into actionable recommendations for FP10 to accelerate research and innovation, strengthen the circular bioeconomy, and position wood at the core of resilient value chains and low-carbon construction.

Key recommendations for Horizon Europe 2028 – 2034
Strategic decisions are needed to integrate wood's renewable and regenerative potential into the Horizon Europe programme 2028–2034. These decisions should encompass fundamental, applied, demonstrative, innovative and educational approaches, and emphasise their synergies. Wood science, technology, and engineering, as part of the wider bioeconomy domain, with links to sustainable forestry and related value chains, must be explicitly included in the new FP10. It is essential that breakthrough knowledge, innovation, and deployment are carried out in close collaboration with society.

Policy Brief
January 2026

Contribution of WoodPoP to the Advanced Materials Act Consultation

The European Wood Policy Platform (WoodPoP) plays a strategic role in shaping framework conditions for sustainable wood-based value chains and in developing evidence-based policy solutions, measures, and recommendations. By fostering dialogue among policymakers, industry, and research, the platform drives supporting Europe's transition to a circular bioeconomy.

Policy Brief
June 2025

The Wood-Based Sector Requires a Skilled Workforce to Propel Europe Towards a Sustainable Future

Background
The wood-based sector (WBS), with 8 million employees is a key player in the transition towards a more innovative, inclusive, and sustainable society, specifically contributing to rural development and the job creation, considering primary and secondary raw materials processing and off-site prefabrication.¹

To advance circular thinking, eco-design, and actions across all stages of processing and product service life, there is a need to enhance the reuse of the relevant product system and its materials, ensuring the efficient use of wood as a renewable and valuable resource. Wood-based construction (WBC) is the most apparent part of the WBS to showcase these efforts, as its products store biologically sequestered carbon throughout their service life¹.

Advanced Materials Act – increasing R&D sustainability, or the materials (as already programmed European) when modified or -based materials are present of critical raw materials key priorities in materials as advanced circularity. of materials prioritised policies, and enhance

Forest Fund
Republic of Austria

An initiative by the Federal Ministry
of Agriculture and Forestry, Climate
and Environmental Protection,
Regions and Water Management
Republic of Austria

With the support of:

Prologue V Health & Well-Being in Timber Buildings

29th International Wood Construction Conference

3 December 2025 | Innsbruck, Austria

European Wood Policy Platform : Towards a wood-based circular bioeconomy

- Pan-European policy dialogue initiative involving 27 countries, 45 stakeholders and industry organisations in one platform
- Voluntary knowledge exchange and joint advocacy actions

Weblinks

woodpop.eu

at.linkedin.com/company/european-wood-policy-platform-woodpop

Višnja Koščak
Secretariat Coordinator

State of the network: Annual report 2025/2026

1. Minutes of GA 2025
2. Welcome to new members
3. A short history of InnovaWood
4. Financial Report & Budget
5. Strategy Process
6. EU Projects
7. IW Internal Projects
- 8. Summary & Conclusions**

In summary:

1. IW has grown into a really strong & visible European network.
2. The Secretariat's competent team and our growing member base are our biggest assets.
3. The Strategy Process guides us to better sharpen our membership services and our USP as EU project partner.
4. We are building up own internal knowledge through synergies of many different EU projects and activities.
5. IW is becoming a recognized voice for R&I in EU advocacy.

25 years Before - After

[no comment]

Networking is the key to excellence

25 years

MWPP | THE MARCUS
WALLENBERG
PRIZE

mwp.org

"The 2026 Marcus Wallenberg Prize is awarded to **Prof. Holger Militz** for his groundbreaking contributions to research on, and industrialization of wood modification technologies."

A big shoutout to the Founding Fathers & Mothers

Mariano Pérez Campos

Ewa Ratajczak

Joris Van Acker

Johannes Welling

Mark Irle

Leena Paavalainen

Gus Verhaeghe

... and many others involved ...

IW Executive Board 2026/2027

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Slovenia - *President*

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Furniture Industry, Belgium

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CESEFOR Foundation,
Spain

Happy Birthday InnovaWood !

25 years

We are looking forward to the next 25 years !